

Assessment of Non-Performing Loans and Financial Performance on Deposit Money Banks (DMB) in Nigeria Banking System

*Aguwamba, S. M.¹

Email: aguwambas.iuokada.edu.ng

Inobemhe, Aliyu Mohammed²

Correspondence E-mail: mohammedinobemhe20@gmail.com

Tel: +2348026662926

¹Department of Banking and Finance, Igbinedion University, Okada, Edo State

²Department of Banking and Finance, School of Business Studies, Auchu Polytechnic, Auchu, Edo State

Abstract

This study investigated the impact of non-performing loans of deposit money banks' (DMBs) performance in Nigeria within a period of twenty-one (21) years, that is 2001 to 2021. The study specifically examined the effect of non-performing loans on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria; and evaluated the extent to which provision for loan-losses have affected DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria. The study used secondary data obtained from annual financial statement of eight selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. The data generated were thematically analysed with the aid of ordinary least square and panel regression analysis. The findings of the study revealed that non-performing loans have unequivocally negative impact on the financial performance on DMBs in Nigeria, thus, reduces both return on assets and return on equity of the banks in Nigeria. The study therefore, offered recommendations including the need for banks to be more proactive and mindful of the provision for loan losses. Thus, this provision should be used as a strategic means for managing loans and ensuring effective prediction of loan behaviour within banks.

Keywords: Non-Performing loans, lending rate, loan-losses, loan behaviour

Introduction

Globally, the banking industry is primarily concerned with accepting deposits from the general public and making those deposits available to credit-worthy borrowers in the form of loans for purchases, investments, and other uses. According to Akinlo and Mofoluwaso (2014), bank credit often includes overdrafts, loans, advances, business funding agreements, local purchase order financing, etc. Thus, one of the core roles of deposit money banks (DMBs) is to provide bank credit, commonly known as lending. In essence, loans stand in for investments and are often included in banks' lengthened assets. People and organizations apply for loans. When a household's surplus of income over expenditure is negative, the households look to banks for loanable funds (Somoye, 2019). DMBs examine criteria such the purpose of the loan, liquidity risk, repayment mechanism, and source of repayment when making loans to people, households, businesses, and governments (Somoye, 2019). As a result, loans and advances made by DMBs are frequently of a temporary nature. This explains why the loan officers' effective and efficient credit analyses are what provide loan portfolios in DMBs their value. As a result, the responsibility of the credit expert is to ensure that loans authorized have a respectable qualitative composition.

In Nigeria, the CBN (2010) mandated through its practical guidelines that licensed banks review their credit portfolios continuously, at least once every quarter, in order to identify any deterioration in credit quality. Additionally, a credit facility should be deemed non-performing once any of the following conditions exist: (i) where interest or principal is due and unpaid for 90 days or more and interest payments equal to 90 days, (ii) interest or more have been capitalized rescheduled or rolled over into a new loan. Thus, they classified non-performing credit facilities into three categories namely, substandard, doubtful or lost (Biabani, Gilaninia & Mohabatkhah, 2012). Therefore, it is unnecessary to explain that sizable NPLs could have a detrimental impact on the level of private investment, raise deposit liabilities, and limit the availability of bank lending to the private sector. Bhattarai (2017) asserts that the failure of banks is the direct result of a high level of non-performing loans in the banking system. Given that the banking system serves as the hub around which other economic sectors operate, any shock to the system would undoubtedly have a detrimental impact on the economy as a whole. Due to significant non-performing loans and worsening cost of efficiency, several banks in emerging nations, including Nigeria, failed between the 1990s and the

Assessment of Non-Performing Loan ... (Aguwanba & Inobemhe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10070221>

early 2000s (Podpiera & Weill, 2008). NPLs were determined to be a significant barrier to banks' profitability in both emerging countries and mature nations, as seen in their balance sheets (Abiola & Olausi, 2014).

According to Somoye (2019), over 10 percent of all loans granted in Nigeria between 1991 and 2018 were NPLs, and this upward tendency has significantly contributed to bank distress. In many instances, bank defaulting debtors were discovered to have abandoned their debt responsibilities and gone to other unknowing banks to get into fresh debt agreements, which were again likely to develop into nonperforming loans. Status updates on a bilateral basis were ineffective in identifying such suspect multiple loan defaulters. As a result, it has become essential to have a single information database from which to get the necessary combined credit information on borrowers. This led to the formation of the Credit Risk Management System by the Central Bank of Nigeria. There are basic economic functions that banks are supposed to carry out. To ensure an effective distribution of the deposits under their care, they must serve as financial intermediaries and facilitate the payment system. The term 'banking' today refers to the indigenous laws and practices of the geopolitical units and units that make up today's Nigeria (Ojo & Somoye, 2016). According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2010), modern banking began in Nigeria in the second half of the nineteenth century, when Elder Dempster began transferring money in specie from one region to another in an effort to expand the nation's shipping industry. As a result, the banking sector existed before Nigeria gained political independence. Many times, a significant buildup of non-performing loans has been linked to the incidence of banking sector failure due to insolvency (Fofack, 2005). The ownership structure, size, and operational reach of the Nigerian banking sector have changed throughout time. Eighty-nine (89) banks operated in Nigeria's banking system before it was consolidated in 2005. This system, known as the universal banking system (UBS), had no restrictions on the share capital investments that banks might make in other financial service industries. Due to the UBS's interconnected subsidiaries, other financial entities with banks as minority or majority shareholders proliferated, and the regulatory institution had supervisory bottlenecks. The development of the Global Financial Crisis (GFC) in 2007-2008 resulted in the decrease in oil prices and drastically reduced profits on investment in the oil industry. The banking system was put in a position of significant credit risk due to the accompanying capital outflow. As the number of non-performing loans increased and had negative economic effects, the asset quality of Nigerian banks drastically declined. The situation exacerbated as a result of the GFC's aftereffects, which caused the banks' non-performing loan (NPL) ratio to reach an all-time high of 37.3 percent in 2009. The banks' capacity to provide loans to the real sector was hampered by their toxic asset glut and severe liquidity issues. Many banks had to scale back operations and reduce spending in order to overcome the obstacles (Vardar & Ozguler, 2015). The borrower must make a cash payment to ensure that the outstanding unpaid interest does not exceed 90 days if: i) interest or principal is due and unpaid for 90 days or more; and ii) interest payment equal to 90 days or more have been capitalized, rescheduled, or rolled over into a new loan (except where facilities have been reclassified as performing). From this study, it can be seen that non-performing loans and bank return on assets in Nigeria primarily have an inverse connection (NDIC, 2018).

This study is anchored on the agency theory. Fadun (2013) asserts that the theory is predicated on the idea that bank managers, who act as agents in this situation, might engage in self-serving activities that could jeopardize the interests of stockholders. In a specific business transaction, the agent represents the principal and is responsible for acting in the principal's best interests, putting the interests of the principal before their own. The agency theory's principal-agent models can be roughly divided into three kinds, each reflecting a fundamental aspect of information asymmetry. The models with ex-post asymmetric information are the first class. After the principal and agent signed the contract, the agent in these models receives certain confidential information. They are referred to as 'moral hazard models.' The models with ex-ante asymmetric information belong to the second class. In these models, the agent already possesses confidential information before the contract is signed. Adverse selection models are what these models are called. The third class of signaling models is closely related. In these models, the informed agent may send the principal a signal that contained his personal information (Shadnam, 2014). Because the agent's ability to cover potential losses in the future is unpredictable, and because the principal is unaware of the needs and wants of the agents, the principal will design the contract to receive some profits from the agents. The principal wants to assign the contract in a way that increases his profit while paying the agent for carrying out the duty that is expected of him (Ibrahim, Saiful & Kayes, 2021).

Cundo, Pandoyo and Mohammad (2022) examined the effects of macroeconomic factors, including inflation projections, and bank-specific characteristics, such as return on asset, equity to asset ratio, and bank size. Data panel analysis was used to analyze the study. The study shows that non-performing loans are significantly impacted negatively by Return on Assets. While inflation has a beneficial impact on non-performing loans, equity to asset ratio and bank size have a large positive impact. Kamal (2022) investigates the impact of non-performing loans on profitability while controlling for operating effectiveness. Multiple regression, route analysis, and descriptive data analysis methods were employed. According to the

Assessment of Non-Performing Loan ... (Aguwanba & Inobemhe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10070221>

study, non-performing loans have a little but positive impact on operating efficiency, whereas operating efficiency has a small but negative impact on profitability. The statistical analysis of the direct impact of non-performing loans on profitability demonstrates that, even in the presence of operating efficiency, non-performing loans have a negative and considerable influence on profitability. The study reveals that the relationship between NPL and ROA is unaffected by operating efficiency. But there is a statistically significant and unfavorable correlation between non-performing loans and profitability. In their study, Joseph & Okike (2021) assessed the effect of non-performing loans on Nigerian bank enterprises' profitability. For a period of ten (10) years, this study used secondary data from the NDI's Annual Report and Statement of Accounts (2010-2019). The statistical methods for regression were used to analyze the data. The outcome showed that there is no correlation between Nigerian banks' return on assets (ROA) and their non-performing loans (NPL). The maximization of shareholder value revealed a connection between Nigerian banks' NPL and Return on Equity (ROE).

Ozurumba (2016) investigated the effect of non-performing loans on the performance of a few commercial banks in Nigeria from 2000 to 2013. The analysis of the study's secondary data, which was derived from the annual reports and accounts of the chosen banks during the study period, used the ordinary least square method and ratio analysis. The findings showed that NPLs and bank performance as assessed by ROE had an adverse connection, with an increase in NPLs leading to a fall in ROE. The study came to the conclusion that the effects of NPLs on banks cannot be understated because they pose a serious danger to the banks' ability to continue operating as corporations.

Objectives of the Study

Therefore, the study specifically:

1. examines the effect of non-performing loans on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria;
2. evaluates the extent to which provision for loan-losses has affected DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria; and
3. ascertains whether lending rate has a significant influence on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study provides answers to the following research questions:

1. Do non-performing loans have effect on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria?
2. Does provision for loan-losses affect DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria?
3. Does lending rate have any significant influence on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria?

Methodology

The study employs a longitudinal research method, which is predicated on the fact that it includes repeated observations of the same variables throughout a 21-year period, from 2001 to 2021. The population of this study consists of all nineteen Nigerian deposit money banks that have been approved and are authorized on a national and international level by the Central Bank of Nigeria. As examples of international Authorization, there are Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc. While Citi Bank Nigeria Limited, Eco Bank Nigeria Plc, Heritage Bank Limited, Keystone Bank Limited, Polaris Bank Plc, Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc, Standard Chartered Bank Ltd, Sterling Bank Plc, Titan Trust Bank Limited, Unity Bank Plc and Wema Bank Plc are Deposit Money Banks with National Authorization. Out of the 19 deposit money banks in Nigeria operating between 2001 and 2021, the study uses eight (8) internationally licensed deposit money institutions as its sample. These include Access Bank Plc, Fidelity Bank Plc, First City Monument Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, Union Bank of Nigeria Plc, United Bank for Africa Plc, and Zenith Bank Plc. This is because for the study's study period, 2001 to 2021, official annual data on the study's variables may be obtained from the proper designated government institutions, including the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). In order to choose which cases to study, the study used judgmental sampling approaches. Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square (FMOLS) and Panel Data Regression were both used in the study's data analysis. In contrast to panel data regression, which covered the eight (8) chosen banks, pooled OLS covered the individual variable data. It is essential to compare the outcomes of the two methods. A panel data methodology was used in the study as well. The term 'fixed effect estimator' is therefore used to describe an estimator for the regression model's coefficients. The fixed effect model's generalized form can be found in;

$$Y_{it} = \delta_0 + \beta X_{it} + \mu_{it} + v_{it} \quad \text{-----} \quad \text{(ii)}$$

Where;

Y_{it} = dependent variable

δ_0 = intercept

Assessment of Non-Performing Loan ... (Aguwanba & Inobemhe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10070221>

βx_{it} = vector of explanatory variable

μ_{it} = individual specific effect

v_{it} = error term

To determine whether the Random Effect Model or Fixed Effect Model is most appropriate for the study, the Hausman Test was employed. The generalized form of the fixed effect model is given by;

MODEL 1

$$ROA = F(NPL, PLL, LDR) \text{-----(iv)}$$

MODEL 11

$$ROE = F(NPL, PLL, LDR) \text{----- (v)}$$

While the econometric form of the model is:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NPL_{it} + \beta_2 PLL_{it} + \beta_3 LDR_{it} + e_{it} \text{----- (vi)}$$

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NPL_{it} + \beta_2 PLL_{it} + \beta_3 LDR_{it} + e_{it} \text{----- (vii)}$$

i = cross-sectional variables from 1, 2, 3-----21

t = time series variables from 1, 2, 3 -----21

e = error term

Where;

ROA_{it} = Return on Assets of bank i at the end of year t proxy for bank performance.

ROE_{it} = Return on Equity of bank i at the end of year t proxy for bank performance.

NPL_{it} = Non-performing loans of bank i at the end of year t

NPL = Non-performing loan

Total Loan

PLL_{it} = Provision for loan losses

Provision for loan loss = Pre-Tax Income + Loan Loss Provision / Net Charge Offs.

LDR_{it} = Lending Rate

Lending Interest Rate = Principal x Rate x Time.

Theoretical expectation is depicted as: $\beta_1, \beta_3 < 0$ and $\beta_2 > 0$

β_0 is to take care of the Constant Variable, β_1 is the coefficient of Non-Performing Loans (NPL) which is less than zero ($\beta_1 < 0$). This is because it is expected to be negatively related to Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). β_2 is the coefficient of Provision for Loan losses (PLL) which is expected to be greater than zero ($\beta_2 > 0$). That is a positive relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigeria is expected. While β_3 is the coefficient of Lending Rate (LDR) which is expected to be less than zero ($\beta_3 < 0$). That is, a negative relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigeria is expected. That is a negative relationship with the Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in Nigerian is expected. This study will use Return on Assets, Return on Equity and net profit margin to capture its dependent variable depicting banks' performance in Nigeria.

Results

Research Question 1

Does provision for loan-losses affect DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Data

<i>Variable</i>	Mean	Max.	Min.	Std. Dev.	Skew.	Kurt.	J-B	Prob.	Obs.
<i>ROA</i>	2.02	34.87	-31.06	4.00	-0.04	56.36	19928.20	0.00	168
<i>ROE</i>	0.37	4.73	-0.47	0.71	3.98	19.23	2286.39	0.00	168
<i>NPL</i>	8.22	41.07	0.88	8.62	1.97	6.45	191.81	0.00	168
<i>PLL</i>	14.33	37.47	-28.00	7.23	-2.37	17.02	1533.27	0.00	168
<i>LDR</i>	63.30	102.31	15.44	18.87	-0.17	2.14	6.05	0.05	168

Source: Authors' computations, 2022

Average non-performing loan ratio (i.e., ratio of the amount of non-performing loans to total loan disbursement) is 8.22, suggesting that about 8.2 percent of loans by deposit money bank selected in the study is lost within the reporting year on average. Thus, banks in Nigeria are performing less effectively in terms of loan administration with the attendant high loan losses in the system. The mean value of NPL is generally positively skewed at 1.97, indicating that more of the non-performing

Assessment of Non-Performing Loan ... (Aguwanba & Inobemhe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10070221>

loans recorded by the banks in our sample are generally less than the reported mean value. However, there are large values of non-performing loans among the banks in the sample, with maximum value of non-performing loan of 41.07 percent. This shows that there are banks in Nigeria that have excessive non-performing loan ratios, and this is quite appalling for these banks. The standard deviation value for the non-performing loan ratio variable is higher than the mean value, which indicates that there is a high level of divergence in the non-performing loan conditions of banks in Nigeria. Average ratio of provision for loan to total loans disbursed is 14.33, indicating that 14 percent of loan disbursed are predicted to be bad loans. This is a high loan failure rate in the banking system in Nigeria. There are different perspectives to this condition in the banking system in Nigeria, including weak internal loan management systems and the ever-present macroeconomic instability that exacerbate the tendency for loan failure in the economy. In relation to this outcome, average loan to deposit ratio (LDR) is 63.3 percent. Given that this variable shows the level of risk-taking by these DMBs, the high LDR shows that more banks are taking high risks in terms of loan disbursement in Nigeria, especially in relation to their liquidity conditions.

For the macroeconomic and policy variables, average inflation rate is also 12.2, which is double digits, with maximum value at 23.79 percent. These are high inflation values for the country and also underscore the risk of difficult loan repayments over the years. Interest rate is 15.8 percent on average with a standard deviation of 4.3, suggesting that the mean value is relatively representative among the economies. Average interest rate is higher than average inflation rate (as to be expected), thus demonstrating that the macroeconomic stability matters for ensuring stable bank lending activities. The Jarque-Bera statistics for all the variables are all significant at the 5 percent level, which shows the absence of normality in their respective data distributions. This outcome is to be expected since a panel of different banks was adopted for the datasets. Hence, the result shows that bank-level characteristics may be exerting strong heterogeneous influences for the behaviour of the datasets. This is a strong basis for providing a panel-form analysis in the regression process for the study.

The variables in the study are also considered in terms of the individual banks in order to highlight the main banks that provide strong dimensions in the data series. The mean and standard deviation of the variables are reported in Table 2. It is seen that the average ROA is highest for Guarantee Trust Bank and Access Bank at 3.8 percent and 3.37 percent respectively. On the other hand, Union Bank had the lowest ROA for the banks at 0.24 percent. Surprisingly, Union Bank also has the highest standard deviation value for the ROA variable, indicating that the bank experienced the highest level of instability in the ROA over the period of the study. UBA has the highest average ROE, indicating that the banks performed better than the others in terms of management of shareholders' funds. Again, Union Bank had the least ROE value of 0.07 on average, which therefore shows that the bank had the least financial performance indicators over the period of the study. For the non-performing loans, the ratio is highest for Union Bank at 14.72 percent. This outcome gives some indication that the bank with the highest non-performing loans also had the poorest financial performance ratios in Nigeria. In terms of loan risk taking however, Access Bank had the highest indication at 74.74 for the loan to deposit ratio, while First Bank was recorded as the biggest bank in the sample as shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Individual Banks

Bank	ROA		ROE		NPL	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. De.
Access Bank	3.37	7.26	0.14	0.10	6.81	4.79
Fidelity Bank	1.31	1.12	0.16	0.13	10.92	9.53
First Bank Holding	1.80	1.11	0.34	0.22	13.54	12.43
First City Monumental Bank	1.39	1.14	0.31	0.42	6.51	7.10
Guaranty Trust Bank	3.80	0.82	0.39	0.57	4.84	3.90
Union Bank of Nig	0.24	8.08	0.07	0.18	14.72	10.79
United Bank for Africa	1.57	0.78	1.05	1.50	5.49	5.62
Zenith Bank	2.67	0.70	0.45	0.83	2.93	1.42
	PLL		LDR			
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.		
Access Bank	15.29	4.81	74.74	15.44		
Fidelity Bank	13.80	6.46	65.52	16.75		

Assessment of Non-Performing Loan ... (Aguwanba & Inobemhe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10070221>

First Bank Holding	12.99	4.93	59.84	10.17
First City Monumental Bank	16.59	4.93	71.32	19.42
Guaranty Trust Bank	16.65	3.25	73.55	18.24
Union Bank of Nig	13.27	16.23	55.76	19.93
United Bank for Africa	11.31	3.64	45.44	15.18
Zenith Bank	14.71	3.29	60.19	16.59

Source: Authors' computations, 2022

Only GTB and Zenith Banks exhibited relatively upward trends in their NPL for the period. This shows that these banks have been having some form of increases in the NPL for the period, although the general ratio is very low for the banks, when compared to banks like Union, Fidelity and First Banks. Thus, it appears that banks with relatively low NPL are those that are experiencing some form of increase over the years. Banks like FCMB, UBA and Access have done quite well in bringing down their NPL from high levels to very low levels over the years. On the other hand, there are strong fluctuations in the NPL of banks like Union, Zenith and First Bank. Generally, the trends in Nigerian banks indicate that there are heavy fluctuations in the rate of non-performing loans, while many banks have succeeded in bringing down their NPL between 2001 and 2021.

Research Question 2

Do non-performing loans, provision for loan losses and Lending rate have significant effect on DMBs' financial performance in Nigeria (ROA)?

The results of the fixed and random effects model for return on assets as the bank performance variable are presented in table 3. It can be seen that the goodness of fit statistics has improved drastically over the pooled OLS estimates in each of the estimations. The goodness of fit statistics values is also better in the fixed effects estimates than in the random effects estimates. The adjusted R-squared value in the fixed effects estimates shows that about 60 percent of systematic variations in ROA for the banks are captured in the model with control, while 63 percent is captured in the model without control. Thus, the focus of the analysis in this study is on fixed effect estimations.

Table 3: Panel Regression Result for the ROA Equation

Variable	<i>Fixed effects</i>				<i>Random effects</i>			
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
Constant	10.534	0.00	8.965	0.00	8.952	0.02	7.504	0.05
NPL	-0.042	0.00	-0.022	0.04	-0.076	0.05	-0.055	0.16
PLL	--	--	0.053	0.00	--	--	0.091	0.05
LDR	-0.002	0.59	-0.005	0.30	0.008	0.68	-0.005	0.79
R-sq.	0.634		0.66		0.062		0.085	
Adj. R-sq.	0.603		0.63		0.027		0.045	
F-stat.	21.502		20.49157		1.761		2.134	

Source: Authors' Computations, 2022

The focus is on the particular contribution of the individual variables to return on asset (ROA) of the banks. This is done by considering the signs and significance of the coefficient of the explanatory variables. In the result, the coefficient of NPL is negative and significant at the 1 percent level in the estimates without PLL and passes the significance test at the 5 percent level for the estimates with PLL (although the coefficient is negative). This result shows that non-performing loans have a significant negative impact on the return on assets of DMBs in Nigeria. The effect of NPL is however stronger for the estimates without PLL than for estimates with PLL included. Thus, the result suggests that the debilitating effect of non-performing loans on ROA is weaker when the provisions for loan losses are not taken into cognizance.

The effectiveness of loan loss provision in boosting ROA of the DMBs is observed by considering that the coefficient of PLL in the model, which is positive and significant at the 1percent level. This result shows that provision for loan losses tend to lead to improvement in ROA of the banks. Thus, banks with effective loan loss provision management tend to perform better in terms of ROA than banks without this mechanism. The coefficient of loan to deposit ratio fails the significance test at the 5 percent level in both estimates, indicating that credit risk-taking of banks does not significantly affect their ROA in Nigeria. This implies that although such risk taking may directly influence the direction of non-performing loans for the DMBs, its direct impact on ROA is not significant. The coefficient of bank size is significant at the 1 percent level for both estimates.

Assessment of Non-Performing Loan ... (Aguwanba & Inobemhe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10070221>

This shows that the size of banks matter for their ROA performance. Essentially, bigger banks are shown to exhibit lower financial performance in terms of return on assets.

For the other external factors in the model, the result shows that the impact of interest rate and inflation rate on ROA of the banks are both insignificant since the coefficients of both variables fail the significance test even at the 5 percent level. Thus, the two factors which are external to the banks are shown as irrelevant in terms of explaining the ROA of the banks over the period of the analysis. Rising interest rates may lead to more incidences of non-performing loans, but they do not influence the ROA of the banks. In the same vein, price changes are shown to be weak in influencing the pattern of return on assets of the DMBS in Nigeria.

Research Question 3

Do non-performing loans, provision for loan losses and Lending rate have significant effect on DMBS' financial performance in Nigeria (ROE)?

The section presents the results of the estimates of the impact of NPL and other variables on ROE of the banks. The adjusted R-squared values for the fixed effects estimates are also larger than those of the pooled OLS and the random effects estimates. This again justifies the efficiency of the fixed effects approach to the estimation for this study. The important focus of the analysis is on the coefficients of the explanatory variables. In the results, the coefficient of NPL is significant at the 1 percent level and is negative. This result supports the outcome of the ROA equation and shows that non-performing loans unequivocally lead to decline in the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria. The negative impact is the same for both the estimates with PLL and without PLL, indicating that the presence of PLL does not influence the impact of NPL on ROE of DMBS in Nigeria. This is unlike the outcome of the ROA equation. The coefficient of PLL in the model is positive and significant at the 1 percent level. This also shows that provision for loan losses has a significant positive impact on the financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria, irrespective of the measure of performance used.

Table 4: Panel Regression Result for the ROA Equation

Variable	Fixed Effects				Random Effects			
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
C	0.985	0.00	0.947	0.00	1.152	0.06	1.171	0.07
NPL	-0.006	0.00	-0.006	0.00	-0.016	0.02	-0.016	0.02
PLL			0.003	0.19			-0.001	0.90
LDR	-0.005	0.00	-0.006	0.00	-0.014	0.00	-0.014	0.00
R-squared	0.469		0.473		0.144		0.144	
Adj.R-squared	0.425		0.425		0.112		0.106	
F-statistic	10.476		9.806		4.505		3.840	

Source: Authors' Computations, 2022

The coefficient of the LDR passes the significance test at the 1 percent level. This shows that the loan risk-taking activities of the DMBS significant limit the return on equity of the banks. Thus, although this risk taking does not affect the asset quality management of the banks, this study shows that it directly reduces the return on equity or the management of shareholders' funds among the banks. Thus, risks on loans are shown to directly be linked to lower shareholders' value rather than asset management of the banks in Nigeria. This is an important aspect of this study where it is demonstrated that risk taking on loans may not influence the asset quality or internal operational management of the banks but the shareholders' funds in the banks. Essentially, there is evidence that the agency problem between the shareholders and the managers is critically triggered when bank managers engage in risking loan management activities. This is because the managers are shown to be prone to pushing the effects on non-performing loans to shareholders' interests rather than directly on the asset management of the banks. The coefficient of both monetary policy rate and inflation rate also fail the significance tests at the 5 percent level. This shows that, just like ROA, the external macroeconomic factors do not have significant impact on the return to equity of DMBS in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study shows that non-performing loans have strong direct and unequivocal negative impact on financial performance of DMBS in Nigeria. This finding is in line with studies by Ibitomi & Micah (2021), and Somoye (2019). The presence of a provision for loan losses in the bank, however, mitigates the unfavorable impacts. The financial performance

Assessment of Non-Performing Loan ... (Aguwanba & Inobemhe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10070221>

indicator of ROA makes this particularly pertinent. Essentially, the conclusion implies that rising non-performing loans affect banks' returns on assets or operational efficiency more severely when loan loss provisions are low. Non-performing loans have a minimal and ineffective influence on ROA when there is a loan loss reserve. This study has shown that loan loss provisions have the ability to reduce the negative effects of non-performing loans on the ROA of DMBs in Nigeria, which is a highly significant finding. These results are consistent with Abdulai, Ahmad and Ajape (2022), Olszak, Chodnicka-Jaworska, Kowalska and Witaa (2018), Arajo, Lustosa and Paulo (2018) and Arbak (2017) who found that loan loss provision, is fundamentally counter-cyclical in Nigeria during times of financial crisis.

Conclusion

The influence of non-performing loans and other associated elements of the Nigerian banking system on the financial performance of these institutions were explored in this study. In order to ensure improvements in performance for the banks in the sampled nations, it has been demonstrated that reducing the non-performing loans in connection to loan and cash management is essential. The study also shows that, despite the fact that increased provisions for loan losses can be a bank's strategic move in projecting default and overall loan failure, these provisions have a negative impact on profitability in Nigeria's banking industry. In essence, risk-controlling in credit activities is a crucial issue in the banking sector, necessitating that bank managers and professionals develop strategic solutions for liquidity management that can reduce credit risks and bad debts. Also, the study has demonstrated that how non-performing loans affect bank financial performance is influenced by how the banks manage their loan loss provisions. Therefore, banks should take a more proactive approach and pay attention to the loan loss provision. These provisions should essentially be used as a strategic tool for controlling loans and guaranteeing accurate loan behavior forecast inside the institutions.

References

- Abdulai, A. S., Ahmad, B. U. & Ajape, K. (2022). Bank loan loss cyclicity in Nigeria: Global versus localeconomic crises effect. *RUJMASS* 8(1).
- Abiola, I., & Olausi, A. S. (2014). The impact of credit risk management on the commercial banks' performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 3(5), 295-306. *Accounting and Taxation*, 6 (2).
- Akinlo, O. & Mofoluwaso, E. (2014). Determinants of non-performing loans in Nigeria. *IBFR*
- Araujo, A. M. H. B. D., Lustosa, P. R. B. & Paulo, E. (2018). The cyclicity of loan loss provisions under three different accounting models: The United Kingdom, Spain, and Brazil. *Revista Contabilidade & Finanças*, 29(76), 97-113.
- Arbak, E. (2017). *Identifying provisioning policies of Belgian banks*. National Bank of Belgium Working Paper Research No. 326. Retrieved from <https://www.nbb.be/doc/ts/publications/wp/wp326en.pdf>
- Bhattarai, Y. R. (2017). Effect of non-performing loan on the profitability of commercial banks in Nepal. *Prestige International Journal of Management and Research*, 10(2), 1-9.
- Biabani, S., Gilaninia, S. & Mohabatkah, H. (2012). Assessment of effective factors on non-performing loans (NPLs) creation: Empirical evidence from Iran (2006-2011). *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 2(10), 10589-10597.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2010). Prudential Guidelines for Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
- Cundo, H. Pandoyo, K. & Mohammad, S. (2022). Factors affecting non-performing loans in state-owned banking. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR) Peer Reviewed -International Journal*, 6(2). Jakarta, Indonesia.
- Fadun, O. S. (2013). Corporate governance and insurance company growth: Challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(1), 286-305.
- Fofack, H. (2005). Nonperforming loans in Sub-Saharan Africa: causal analysis and macroeconomic implications. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper (3769).
- Ibitomi, T. & Micah, E. E. M. (2021). Empirical Analysis of Non-Performing Loans and Liquidity of Deposit Money Banks: Nigeria Experience. *Journal of International Business and Management (JIBM)* 4(9):01-14. University of Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.
- Ibrahim, M. Saiful, I. & Kayes, B. R. (2021). Corporate Governance Structure and bank performance. Evidence from and emerging economy. *Journal of Economic and administrative sciences*.

Assessment of Non-Performing Loan ... (Aguwanba & Inobemhe, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10070221>

- Joseph, F. A. & Okike B. M. (2021). The impact of non-performing loans on firm profitability: A focus on the Nigerian banking industry. *American Research Journal of Business and Management*, 1(4). Nigerian College of Accountancy, Kwall near Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.
- Kamal, U. (2022). The effect of non-performing loan on state-owned commercial banks' profitability with operating efficiency as mediating variable. Department of Accounting and Information Systems, Islamic University, Bangladesh. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(3).
- Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC, 2018). Annual report and statement of account.
- Olszak, M., Chodnicka-Jaworska, P., Kowalska, I. & Świtała, F. (2018). Bank-type specific determinants of sensitivity of loan-loss provisions to business cycle. *The European Journal of Finance*, 16(17), 1672-1698.
- Ozurumba, B. A. (2016). Impact of non-performing loans on the performance of selected commercial banks in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(16).
- Podpiera, J. & Weill, L. (2008). Bad luck or bad management? Emerging banking market experience. *Journal of financial stability*, 4(2), 135-148.
- Shadnam, M. (2014). The mathematics of principal-agent problem with adverse selection. *Journal of Mathematics*, 6(1).
- Somoye, R. O. C. (2019). The variation of risks on non-performing loans on banks performances in Nigeria. *Indian Journal of Economics & Business*, 9(1), 87-99.
- Vardar, G., & Ozguler, I. C. (2015). Short term and long-term linkages among nonperforming loans, macroeconomic and bank-specific factors: An empirical analysis for Turkey. *15(3)*, 313.